

TEACHING AND LEARNING STRATEGIES IN ENHANCING VOCABULARY COMPETENCY TOWARDS DESIGNING A DIGITAL WORKTEXT

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ABSTRACT

Mastery of skills in the second language highly requires enhancement of vocabulary competency. As such, the researcher believes that the country's educational system needs to step up its efforts in improving the teaching and learning strategies in terms of enhancing vocabulary. This study aimed to assess the extent of utilization of teaching strategies in four macro-skills and vocabulary strategies. It also covered the relationships between the extent of utilization of teaching and vocabulary strategies and identify online media features in accessing instructional learning materials. Descriptive method was employed in this study. The results of the study revealed that teaching and vocabulary strategies were utilized in a moderate extent. There is a significant relationship between teaching strategies in reading and discovery-determination, consolidation-memory, consolidation-cognitive and consolidation-metacognitive while it concluded no significant relationship in consolidation-social. Teaching strategies in listening disclosed significant relationship in vocabulary strategies such as consolidation-memory, consolidation-cognitive and consolidation-metacognitive strategies while it exposed no significant relationship among discovery-determination and consolidation-social strategies. Moreover, teaching strategies in speaking indicated significant relationship in all vocabulary strategies. Finally, the teaching strategies in writing demonstrated significant relationship in discovery-determination, consolidation-memory and consolidation-cognitive strategies whereas it indicated no significant relationship in consolidation-social and consolidation-metacognitive strategies. Furthermore, student-respondents agreed that providing connections to other digital media like wiki or blogs, generating quizzes, showing updates in horizontal form through scrollable timeline are the features of online media platforms in accessing instructional learning materials. The designed digital worktext is envisioned to provide different teaching and learning strategies comprised in activities, assessment exercises and applications of vocabulary strategies.

Keywords: Teaching Instruction, Teaching and Vocabulary Learning Strategies, Descriptive Method, Philippines